

Multiscale Modelling: Yarn Deformation to Draping Simulation of Woven Preforms

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SUMMARY

The objective is to simulate the forming forces in a woven preform draped over a complex surface and loaded at its boundaries. The methodology developed here can identify areas of wrinkling. Multiscale modelling approach has been employed in order to eliminate the uncertainties of material testing at intermediate scales.

Keywords: Multiscale modelling, yarn, mesoscale, draping, woven preforms

MULTISCALE MODELLING

Composites Industry mainly uses kinematic draping software such as FibreSIM [1], ignoring the forming forces. PAM-FORM [2] does incorporate forming forces. However, measurement of input constitutive properties such as in-plane shear is unreliable. This paper presents a multi-scale modelling approach starting from fibre properties to full drape model. Based on fibre properties and inter-fibre friction, mechanical models of various modes of yarn deformation have been developed. The output of these models constitutes the inputs of the mesoscale model for fabric deformation. Finally the results of both yarn and fabric deformation models are used to simulate draping of woven fabric composites on complex surfaces. Figure 1 illustrates the state of the materials for the various models.

Figure 1a) Yarn Level

b) Meso-scale Level

c) Draped Configuration

In this paper a model to obtain the bending modulus from fibre properties of a yarn is first described. Other mechanical properties of yarns, such as tensile, can also be easily simulated [3]. The computed yarn properties together with fabric parameters are the inputs to biaxial [4] and shear deformation modelling of the fabric. The shear model is outlined in this paper. Finally an approximate force analysis has been demonstrated in conjunction with a kinematic drape algorithm. The primary objectives of the force analysis are to compute:

- Pressure distribution between the tooling and individual plies. For a given coefficient of friction, inter-ply ply shear forces can be computed from the normal forces.
- Thread tensions.
- Regions prone to buckling for given in-plane shear properties and applied external forces.

YARN BENDING

Deformation of Filament due to Yarn Bending

When a yarn is bent to a curvature $\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial s}$, as shown in Figure 2, the strain in any filament, assumed to follow a helical path, is:

$$\varepsilon = y \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial s} (\cos^2 \alpha - \sigma \cdot \sin^2 \alpha) \quad (1)$$

where y is the distance from the centre line of the yarn, α is the helix angle & σ is the yarn Poisson ratio.

Figure 2: Yarn bending under uniform curvature $\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial s}$

At any other cross-section $y = R \sin\left(\frac{2\pi i}{K} + \frac{s \tan \alpha}{R}\right)$ (2)

where R is the helix radius,

K is the number of filaments located at distance R from the centre of the yarn.
 i is the filament number.

Hence $\varepsilon = (\cos^2 \alpha - \sigma \cdot \sin^2 \alpha) R \sin\left(\frac{2\pi i}{K} + \frac{s \tan \alpha}{R}\right) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial s}$ (3)

Energy Considerations: Virtual Work

Using the principle of virtual work the relationships between external forces & moments and strains for the yarn are derived in the following analysis.

The incremental strain energy of a single filament is:

$$\delta U_i = \iiint_{v_i} \varepsilon_i \delta \varepsilon_i dv_i \quad (4)$$

where $dv = A \cdot \frac{s}{\cos \alpha}$

Summing up for the filaments in the yarn:

$$\delta U = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta U_i + \delta U_c \quad (5)$$

where δU_c is the variation of strain energy of the core filament.

N is the number of filaments in the yarn.

The variation in strain energy can be expressed in terms of filament properties by substituting equation (3) in equation (4). Since at equilibrium, the potential energy $M\delta(\Delta\psi)$ is equal to change in strain energy δU an expression for moment can be derived as follows:

$$M = \frac{1}{2} A.E. \sum_{n=0}^N R_n^2 \frac{\Delta\psi}{L} \left(\cos^3 \alpha_n - 2\sigma \cdot \cos \alpha_n \cdot \sin^2 \alpha_n + \sigma^2 \frac{\sin^4 \alpha_n}{\cos \alpha_n} \right) + \frac{1}{4} A.E.r^2 \frac{\Delta\psi}{L} \quad (6)$$

where r is the radius of a filament.

A is the filament area of cross-section.

E is the Young's modulus.

Figure 3: Simulated Yarn Bending

Equation (6) can be modified to account for slippage when forces between filaments exceed friction. The filaments which slip behave independently to the rest of the filaments in the yarn with loss in overall bending rigidity of the yarn. Figure 3 shows the results of simulating bending of a 15 Tex yarn with 75 filaments.

SHEAR MODEL: BIAS EXTENSION

Initial Shear Stiffness

Grosberg and Park [5] produced a mathematical analysis for predicting shear behaviour of woven fabrics. The shear model developed here is based on the Grosberg approach [5] as well as that of Skelton [6]. At low levels of shear stress there is not enough moment available to move the yarns in the fabric at the interaction regions and they behave as if they were welded junctions. In this case deformation takes place in the free length between crossover regions and the deformation is essentially that of cantilever. A set of differential equations developed for modelling plane elastica [4] are integrated to obtain the moment at yarn crossover point, given the deformation. The solution is obtained through solving a boundary value problem with one unknown initial value, the curvature at the 'welded junction' and with zero curvature, halfway along the free yarn length, as boundary value.

Shear Deformation beyond Initial Region

As soon as the stresses are large enough to overcome the frictional restraints that are acting at the crossover regions the system start to slip. The shear stiffness then remains fairly constant until transverse distortion of the yarns causes a sharp increase in stiffness. The mechanism of fabric shear is quite complicated. Once the yarns start to slip, the friction couple increases with shear load due to increase in normal loads at the intersections. Also the yarn paths, hence curvatures, in the fabric are changing with shear deformation, hence further bending is required. If it is assumed that the contact area is circular with diameter equal to the major diameter, a , of the yarn, then friction couple is:

$$T = \mu \frac{4F_y}{\pi a^2} \int_0^{a/2} \frac{2\pi a^2}{4} dr = \frac{1}{3} \mu F_y a \quad (7)$$

The normal load, F_y , depends on the axial load in the yarn and is obtained from the biaxial model of the woven fabric [4]. The axial load for shear force F , shown in Figure 4a is $F \cos \theta$, where θ is half the angle between warp and weft. The moment, M , due to change in yarn path curvature is given below:

$$M = E_b \sin^2(45 - \theta).p \quad (8)$$

where p is the curvature of the yarn path, at intersections, in the orthogonal or undeformed fabric. The relationship between shear load and deformation is therefore:

$$F \sin \theta = E_b \sin^2(45 - \theta).p + \frac{1}{3} \mu F_y a \quad (9)$$

Figure 4a shows the bias extension of woven fabric and Figure 4b illustrates the forces on a unit cell taken from the fabric in Figure 4a. Figure 5 shows the simulation results for glass fibre fabric with yarn bending rigidity of 0.6 Nmm². The graph indicates that the general behaviour of shear deformation is achieved by the model.

Figure 4a: Bias Extension

Figure 4b: Deformed Unit Cell

Figure 5: Simulation Result of Shear Model

DRAPING SIMULATION

Mechanics of Curved Membranes [7]

Tensor \mathbf{T} is the stress tensor. The force acting on element ds , in length, and with unit normal \mathbf{e} , is $\mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{e} ds$ as shown in Figure 6.

For equilibrium:

$$\int_c \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{e} ds + \iint_s p \mathbf{n} dS = 0 \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{n} is unit normal to surface and p is pressure

Using divergence theorem:

$$\iint_s (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{T} + p \mathbf{n}) dS = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Hence } \nabla \cdot \mathbf{T} + p \mathbf{n} = 0 \quad (12)$$

In general $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{T} = T_{,\alpha}^{\alpha\beta} \mathbf{g}_\beta + K_{\alpha\beta} T^{\alpha\beta} \mathbf{n}$ (13)

where $T_{,\alpha}^{\alpha\beta}$ is the surface covariant derivative of tensor \mathbf{T} .

$K_{\alpha\beta}$ is the surface curvature tensor.

\mathbf{g}_u and \mathbf{g}_v are the curvilinear base vectors.

Figure 6: Membrane subjected to pressure and edge forces

The first tensor equation is given by the covariant derivative of tensor T :

$$T_{,\alpha}^{\alpha\beta} = 0 \quad (14)$$

This equation can be expanded into a set of 2 equations when expressed in coordinate form.

The second tensor equation $K_{\alpha\beta} T^{\alpha\beta} + p = 0$ is equivalent to the following:

$$p = -K_{uu} T^{uu} - 2K_{uv} T^{uv} - K_{vv} T^{vv} \quad (15)$$

Application to Draped Fabrics

The objective is to compute the pressure distribution, the tensile forces in the yarns given the external load. The stress tensor, defined in the local basis, acting in the fabric at its boundary is given from the transformation law of tensor components:

$$T^{ij} = \frac{\partial x^i}{\partial \bar{x}^k} \frac{\partial x^j}{\partial \bar{x}^l} \bar{T}^{kl} \quad (16)$$

where \bar{T}^{kl} is the external force per unit length on the fabric boundary and \bar{x}^k are the Cartesian coordinates

The stress tensor T^{ij} using equation (14) is computed successively at all the crossover points of the deformed fabric starting from those at the boundary. Equation (14) can be written more explicitly as equation (17) below.

$$T^{\alpha\beta}_{,\alpha} = \frac{\partial T^{\alpha\beta}}{\partial x^\alpha} + \Gamma_{k\alpha}^\alpha T^{k\beta} + \Gamma_{k\alpha}^\beta T^{\alpha k} = 0 \quad (17)$$

where x^α is the local coordinate u or v .

The coordinates of the crossover points are obtained by implementing a draping algorithm [8]. The tension on any small slice through the fabric having width ∇s and unit normal vector \mathbf{e} tangential to the lateral surface is $\mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{e} \nabla s$. To compute the force perpendicular to a yarn segment linking nodes $(u1, v1)$ to $(u2, v2)$ the unit normal vector to the segment is first obtained. This is given from the following:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u2 - u1 & v2 - v1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} E & F \\ F & G \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_u \\ n_v \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (18)$$

where n_u and n_v are the components, in the local basis, of the normal

The pressure at each node is obtained, after the stress tensor has been calculated, by application of the equation (15). Figure 7 shows the distribution of pressure exerted on the surface by the fabric for a load of 0.1N per mm. The maximum pressure occurs at the red area near the pole of the sphere when the external force is applied vertically at the lower boundary of the octant.

Figure 7: Pressure Distribution

Fabric Buckling

Buckling of the draped fabric may occur depending on the external load, the shear properties of the fabric as well as the shear deformation. The areas, colored blue, in Figures 8b and 8c indicate where potentially buckling of the fabric may occur when draped manually or otherwise on a surface. The shear modulus values were 0.01, 0.1 and 0.2 N/mm per radian for the low, median and high shear modulus respectively.

Buckling occurs in a unit cell if the tension in yarns that make up a unit cell is not enough to sustain the shear deformation demanded by the draping process and the geometry of the surface

Figure 8a: Low Shear Modulus

Figure 8b: Medium Shear Modulus

Figure 8c: High Shear Modulus

CONCLUSIONS

A yarn bending model based on fibre properties has been described. The yarn mechanical properties are then used to simulate the tensile and shear behaviour of woven fabrics. An approximate method of analyzing the mechanics of a draped fabric has also been presented. The method is computationally very efficient. This approach may be useful to the designer of fabric reinforced composites as the traditional FE approach is computationally very expensive. By adjusting the external load and given the fabric shear property one may quickly ascertain problem regions when draping a woven fabric. Further to this, pressure distribution can be used to compute inter-ply frictional forces. This computationally efficient force/wrinkle analysis may be implemented to extend the capability of kinematic drape models in order to complement full-scale FE analysis.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Some of the work reported in this publication was carried out under the Technology Strategy Board's collaborative research and development programme, through Project No: TP/5/MAT/6/I/H0558C 'Multi-Scale Integrated Modelling for High Performance Flexible Materials'. The authors would like to thank Technology Strategy Board for financial support, and acknowledge the participation of the industrial and academic partners involved in this project: University of Nottingham, Herriot-Watt University, Technitex, Unilever, ScotCad, Hield, AIL, Croda, OCF, and Carrington.

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